

STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN BIOLOGY THROUGH CRITICAL THINKING CYCLE LEARNING MODEL

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, the importance of critical thinking in education has gained significant attention, leading educators to explore innovative teaching strategies that foster this essential skill. This study investigated the effectiveness of the Critical Thinking Cycle Learning Model on students' academic achievement in biology. Utilizing a quasi-experimental design, the research involved two intact sections of grade 12 STEM students at Kalilangan National High School. Thirty-three (33) students were exposed to the CTCLM, while thirty-one (31) students were exposed to a non-CTCLM. Assessment tools included a questionnaire measuring academic outcomes. Descriptive statistics were applied to evaluate students' academic achievement, while analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was employed to identify significant differences between the two groups. Pretest scores served as a covariate. The findings showed that learners taught using the CTCLM and those taught with non-CTCLM did not meet the expected level of academic achievement. However, CTCLM demonstrated a greater increase in academic achievement after implementation compared to the non-CTCLM group. ANCOVA results confirmed significant differences in achievement between the two groups. Generally, the CTCLM helped learners improve their academic achievement and enhance their critical thinking disposition.

Keywords: *critical thinking cycle learning model, academic achievement, critical thinking disposition*

INTRODUCTION

Science education aims to develop students' extensive grasp of concepts and ability to apply this knowledge effectively in real-life contexts. In the Philippines, due to implementing the K-12 Enhanced Basic Education program, the curriculum is undergoing significant transformations in curriculum design, approach, student outcomes, instructional design, and educational policies. The program seeks to address the demands and challenges of the 21st century (Ramos, 2018).

The poor performance of Filipino students in international and national assessments, such as the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA), Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS), and National Achievement Test (NAT) evaluations, has prompted a comprehensive review of the Philippines' educational system (Malipot, 2019). Science, particularly Biology, is one of the least mastered subjects among Filipino students, contributing to significant academic challenges, especially in high school (Junco & Nabua, 2023). In the Division of Bukidnon, which includes Kalilangan National High School, the 2022 RX Adobe Assessment Results of grade 12 students revealed that the academic achievement of the learners did not reach the minimum proficiency level of 75%, wherein the means scores and proficiency level in science ranged from 32.90 to 46.53%, indicating low proficiency (DEDP, 2023). This underscores the necessity of addressing this concern to improve student performance.

In order to effectively address the issue of students' understanding and performance in science, it is crucial to prioritize developing critical thinking abilities due to the strong link between academic achievement, specifically in the intellectual processes of synthesizing, analyzing, and evaluating (Ali & Awan, 2021; Nur'azizah et al., 2021). Being disposed to critical thinking allows learners to solve problems effectively and make rational choices, and plays a significant role in improving educational performance (Amin et al., 2020).

Fikriyatii et al. (2022) proposed a critical thinking cycle learning model, which was tested with student teachers and has proven its validity and practicality. The model incorporates exercises primarily focused on the critical thinking process, which can positively impact students' academic performance. Wicaksana et al. (2019) also corroborate this observation indicating that, when students are engaged in critical thinking activities, they perform better academically.

Despite the initial findings, further investigation is necessary to examine the implementation of the learning model across different educational levels and its effectiveness on students' academic achievement. Hence, this study investigated the effectiveness of the critical thinking cycle learning model on the academic achievement of high school students in biology. The study findings may also be beneficial for curriculum developers, school principals, and teachers in upgrading the current curriculum to meet the needs of 21st-century science education.

Research Questions

This study generally investigated the effectiveness of the critical thinking cycle learning model on students' academic achievement in biology. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of academic achievement in the pretest and posttest scores of students exposed to the critical thinking cycle learning model (CTCLM) and those exposed to non-CTCLM?
2. Is there a significant difference between students' academic achievement in the pretest and posttest scores exposed to the critical thinking cycle learning model (CTCLM) and those exposed to non-CTCLM?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a quasi-experimental design using a pretest-posttest approach to assess the academic achievement of students. The participants consisted of two heterogeneous sections of Grade 12 STEM students at Kalilangan National High School in Bukidnon. Thirty-three (33) learners were exposed to the Critical Thinking Cycle Learning Model (CTCLM), which consists of six phases: Thinking Issue/Problem, Teaching Critical Thinking through Modeling, Seeking Truth and Exploration, Thinking Together: Explaining and Discussing with Experts, Conducting Implementation Trials, and Evaluating Critical Thinking. Meanwhile, thirty-one (31) learners were exposed to the non-CTCLM approach, which utilized traditional teaching methods based on the 7E's to impart the specific concepts outlined in the table of specifications of the research instrument. A pretest and posttest were administered to assess the students' levels of academic achievement and to determine the significant differences between the CTCLM and non-CTCLM.

The research instrument utilized fifty (50) multiple-choice questions designed to measure the academic achievement levels of students. It was developed based on topics covered in the fourth quarter, specifically plant and animal organ systems and their functions, as well as feedback mechanisms. To ensure the validity of the questionnaires, they were reviewed by three experts for content appropriateness and overall validity. The overall validity score of 4.53 indicates that the instrument is considered to be very valid. The Scale-level Content Validity Index (S-CVI) of 0.934 is excellent, demonstrating strong content validity. Additionally, a pilot test was conducted with BS Biology students at Central Mindanao University, who had completed the STEM strand during their Senior High School years. The reliability coefficient of the questionnaire was calculated at 0.797, indicating strong internal consistency. Ultimately, thirty-five (35) multiple-choice questions were retained for the study. The interpretations of the results were based on the criteria outlined in DepEd Order No. 8, series of 2019.

Descriptive statistics, such as mean, frequency, and percentages, were used to determine the levels of students' academic achievement among those exposed to the

critical thinking cycle learning model (CTCLM) and those exposed to the non-CTCLM. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to determine the significant differences in students' academic achievement between the experimental and control groups, with pretest scores serving as a covariate to control for initial group differences.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data revealed in Table 1 that in the posttest, 78.9% of the CTCLM group still scored below 74, showing some improvement from 100% in the pretest, but they remained below the expected performance level. A small percentage (15.2%) achieved scores between 80 and 84, categorized as satisfactory, while 3.0% scored between 75 and 79, deemed fairly satisfactory. Similarly, the non-CTCLM group scored 90.5% below 74, reflecting a slight improvement from the pretest, but still not meeting expectations. In this group, 3.2% scored between 80 and 84, and 6.5% scored between 75 and 79, both categorized as fairly satisfactory. It is important to note that the mean percentage scores (MPS) indicate that the CTCLM group improved from 34.29 in the pretest to 64.59 in the posttest, while the non-CTCLM group improved from 42.58 to 56.77. Despite some progress, neither group met satisfactory performance levels.

Table 1. Level of Academic Achievement of Students in Pretest and Posttest

Transmuted Grade	PRETEST				POSTTEST				Qualitative Interpretation
	CTCLM		NON-CTCLM		CTCLM		NON-CTCLM		
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
90 – 100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Outstanding
85 – 89	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Very Satisfactory
80 – 84	0	0	0	0	5	15.2	1	3.2	Satisfactory
75 – 79	0	0	0	0	1	3.0	2	6.5	Fairly Satisfactory
Below 74	33	100	31	100	27	78.9	28	90.5	Did Not Meet Expectation
MPS	34.29		42.58		64.59		56.77		
QI	Did Not Meet Expectation		Did Not Meet Expectation		Did Not Meet Expectation		Did Not Meet Expectation		

This is likely because the high heat index and elevated temperatures negatively impact academic performance. The study took place in Bukidnon, where, during the second week of April 2024, the heat index reached "extreme caution" levels, indicating a risk of heat cramps and exhaustion, according to DOST-PAGASA. Bukidnon specifically recorded a heat index of 41°C. As a result, students struggled to concentrate, and more importantly, the classrooms lacked essential appliances like electric fans to help cool the environment. This made it even harder for them to focus during lessons, as a comfortable setting is crucial for effective learning.

Supporting these observations, the study by Miranda et al. (2024) examined the impact of increased seasonal heat on education in the Philippines. Researchers analyzed the sentiments of students and teachers and identified key themes through topic modeling. The findings revealed that higher classroom temperatures lead to negative

emotions such as discomfort, frustration, and decreased motivation. These feelings are closely linked to difficulties in concentration, academic engagement, and overall performance. Furthermore, the study emphasizes how heat stress contributes to attendance issues and higher stress levels, highlighting the urgent need for adaptive measures like improved cooling systems, flexible scheduling, and increased awareness to foster a more conducive learning environment.

Nevertheless, even though both groups scored low on the posttest, it is important to note that the CTCLM group performed better than the non-CTCLM group. This difference can be attributed to the CTCL model, which integrates continuous reflection and evaluation, encourages collaborative discussions with experts, and promotes independent application of critical thinking skills. This approach emphasizes not only knowledge acquisition but also the rational evaluation of claims and evidence, leading to higher academic achievement compared to non-CTCLM.

As stated by Research by Ali and Awan (2021), Safitri et al. (2018), and Adams (2017) stated that critical thinking positively influences academic performance, aligning with the results of this study. These studies demonstrate that students who engage in critical thinking are better equipped to analyze complex information, solve problems creatively, and make informed decisions. Moreover, the critical thinking cycle learning model incorporates activities focusing on the critical thinking process, which can further positively influence students' academic achievement. Wicaksana et al. (2019) also support this, noting that engaging students in critical thinking activities leads to improved academic outcomes.

Table 2. Analysis of Covariance of the Students' Academic Achievement

Group	N	Mean	SD
Critical Thinking Cycle Learning Model (CTCLM)	33	64.589	14.070
Non-CTCLM	31	56.774	11.041
TOTAL	64	60.804	13.103

Source	SS	df	MS	F-value	Sig.
Group	17258.805	2	8269.402	53.644	.000**
Pretest (Covariate)	26.957	1	26.957	.168	.684ns
Error	9812.738	61	160.865		
Total	247428.571	64			

Table 2 shows the analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) of the posttest results for both critical thinking cycle learning model (CTCLM) and non-CTCLM groups using the pre-test as the covariate. The CTCLM (n = 33, SD = 14.07) and non-CTCLM (n = 31, SD = 11.04) groups gained a mean score of 64.59 and 56.77, respectively. The pretest result showed no significance.

The F-value between groups is 53.64, with a p-value of 0.000, indicating statistical significance. This result suggests that the Critical Thinking Cycle Learning Model and the non-CTCLM led to different levels of academic achievement in Biology. The data shows

that the group using the CTCLM performed at a higher academic level compared to the non-CTCLM. Consequently, the null hypothesis, which stated that there was no significant difference in the academic achievement of students exposed to the CTCLM versus those exposed to the non-CTCLM, is rejected. Furthermore, the data indicates that the CTCLM positively impacts students' academic achievement in Biology.

Given this result, a significant difference is clear between the academic achievement of students who were exposed to the CTCLM and those who were taught using the non-CTCLM. The CTCLM promotes the development of critical thinking through activities such as question-and-answer sessions, group and class discussions, truth-seeking, exploration, elaboration, and evaluation. In particular, students are introduced to an issue or problem at the outset, as outlined in Phase 1. This initial framing encourages them to engage with the material actively and think critically from the very beginning. By confronting a real-world challenge, students are more motivated to seek solutions and explore diverse viewpoints.

These activities align with Piaget's constructivist theory, which asserts that individuals actively build their knowledge through personal experiences and interactions with others and their environment (Sutoyo et al., 2023). Additionally, the CTCLM emphasizes the enhancement of students' critical thinking skills, incorporating Facione's principles that stress the importance of analyzing and assessing information, reasoning, and arguments. Furthermore, information-sharing activities, such as discussions and question-and-answer sessions, are highly recommended for developing critical thinking (Sutoyo et al., 2023). These activities are central to the CTCLM and align with social learning theory. This focus may help explain the model's positive impact on students' academic achievement in Biology. Fitriani et al. (2020) note that critical thinking can influence learning outcomes, and Orhan (2022) findings further support this by showing a significant correlation between critical thinking and students' success in the subject.

Conclusions

This implies that adopting the CTCLM positively influences students' academic achievement. Both the CTCLM and non-CTCLM groups initially received a "Did Not Meet Expectations" rating on the pretest. Post-implementation data showed that performance remained below the expected level. This is likely a result of the high heat index, which impacts their concentration in class and leads to lower academic achievement. However, it is important to note that both groups demonstrated increased MPS post-intervention, with the CTCLM group ultimately surpassing the non-CTCLM group. In addition, a significant difference was revealed when exposed to CTCLM and non-CTCLM. This indicates that CTCLM positively affects student learning, resulting in higher post-test scores. The CTCLM incorporates various elements that enhance engagement, such as

collaborative learning, structured inquiry, and critical thinking exercises, which foster deeper understanding.

Recommendations

Future researchers may explore its implementation across grade levels and various scientific disciplines. Design studies that assess immediate academic outcomes and track the long-term effects on students. Consider conducting longitudinal studies to evaluate the sustained impact of CTCLM on student learning over multiple academic years.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors affirm that this study adhered to all ethical guidelines. Informed consent was secured from all participants prior to their involvement, and they were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without any negative consequences. The privacy and anonymity of all participants were safeguarded, with personal information kept confidential. The well-being of the participants was prioritized throughout the research process. There were no conflicts of interest related to this study.

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